

A manuscript of al-Sanūsī’s *Umm al-barāhīn* from Palembang. Interlinear translation as paratext

Aglaia A. Iankovskaia

University of London (London, United Kingdom);
ai30@soas.ac.uk; ORCID: 0000-0003-0567-6627

Abstract. The article addresses interlinear translation from Arabic to vernaculars as practised in the Indonesian-Malay world up to the 20th century. Drawing on the example of a manuscript of a popular Islamic creed, it discusses interlinear translation as a specific form of paratext, which, crossing linguistic borders, mediates between the text and its readers. The manuscript is a copy of the doctrinal treatise *Umm al-barāhīn* (‘Mother of arguments’) by Abū ‘Abdallāh Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf al-Sanūsī al-Tilimsānī (d. 1490), originating from Palembang, Sumatra, and dated to 1843. Digitised by the DREAMSEA project, it is catalogued with the number DS 0008 00001. The copy represents a graphic example of a multi-layered manuscript containing a text and a variety of paratexts, i.e. translations and commentaries, that was typical of Malay Islamic manuscript culture. The article focuses on the interlinear translation from Arabic to Malay found in the manuscript and explores the paratextual features of this writing practice, discussing the power relations between the source text and its translation and attempting a description of interlinear translation as a regionally specific type of paratext at a certain stage of its historical development. Building on Gérard Genette’s questionnaire for paratextual elements, the author defines spatial, temporal, functional, and other features of interlinear translation, pointing to its ability to control and shape the readers’ reception of the text.

Keywords: interlinear translation, paratext, bilingual manuscripts, Malay manuscripts, Arabic manuscripts, Islamic manuscripts, *Umm al-barahin*.

Acknowledgements. This work was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (project ‘Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies’, grant agreement no. 101001731); and by the Israel Science Foundation (grant no. 2009/19).

Рукопись «Умм ал-барāхйн» из Палембанга. Межстрочный перевод как паратекст

А. А. Янковская

Лондонский университет (Лондон, Великобритания);
ai30@soas.ac.uk; ORCID: 0000-0003-0567-6627

Аннотация. Статья посвящена практике межстрочного перевода с арабского на местные языки, распространенной в малайском мире вплоть до XX в. На примере рукописи популярного в традиционном исламском образовании краткого катехизиса межстрочный перевод рассматривается как особая форма паратекста, преодолевающая языковые границы и выступающая посредником между текстом и его читателями. Рукопись представляет собой копию богословского труда «Умм ал-барāхйн» («Мать доводов») авторства Абу ‘Абдаллāха Мухаммада ибн Йўсуфа ал-Санўси ал-Тилимсāни (ум. 1490). Оцифрованная проектом DREAMSEA, она происходит из г. Палембанг, Южная Суматра, и датируется 1843 г. Копия представляет собой яркий образец малайской мусульманской рукописной культуры, объединяющий в себе текст и наслоения паратекстов различных типов, в том числе переводов и комментариев. Основное внимание в статье уделяется содержащемуся в рукописи межстрочному переводу с арабского на малайский, отражающему характерную для региона практику, известную как *kitab jenggotan* (‘бородастые книги’) или *makna gandhul* (‘подвешенное значение’). На основе сформулированного Жераром Женеттом опросника в статье предлагается опыт описания пространственных, временных, функциональных и других особенностей межстрочного перевода. Автор рассматривает паратекстуальные черты этой практики, затрагивая иерархические отношения между исходным текстом и переводом и указывая на способность последнего влиять на восприятие текста читателем.

Ключевые слова: межстрочный перевод, паратекст, двуязычные рукописи, малайские рукописи, арабские рукописи, мусульманские рукописи, *Умм ал-барāхйн*.

Благодарности. Это исследование было поддержано Европейским исследовательским советом (ERC) в рамках исследовательской и инновационной программы Европейского Союза «Горизонт 2020» (проект «Текстовые микрокосмы: новый подход в исследованиях перевода», грантовое соглашение № 101001731), а также Израильским научным фондом (грант № 2009/19).

1. Introduction

Before having been pushed to the foot of the page or end of a chapter, and becoming foot- and endnotes in a printed book, glosses and commentaries thrived in manuscript cultures of Europe and Asia. On pages of manuscripts, they surrounded and enshrouded the main text, occupying wide marginal and interlinear spaces. In the Islamic world, where texts in Arabic spread far beyond its Arabic-speaking heartlands, interlinear spaces were sometimes occupied by translations to local languages. Such “translations” tended to closely follow the source, but sometimes digressed from it into what could be rather described as commentaries — but in a different language. Stemming from the practices of rendering the Quran, they were indeed seen as commentaries [Riddell 2002: 10]. This essay addresses interlinear translation from Arabic as practised in the Indonesian-Malay region up to the 20th century. Drawing on the example of a manuscript of a popular Islamic creed, it discusses interlinear translation as a specific form of paratext, which, crossing linguistic borders, mediates between the text and its readers.

The manuscript is a copy of the doctrinal treatise *Umm al-barāhīn* (“Mother of arguments”) by the North African theologian Abū ‘Abdallāh Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf al-Sanūsī al-Tilimsānī (d. 1490), dated to 1259 AH / 1843 AD. Digitised by the DREAMSEA project, the manuscript is accessible on the latter’s website with the number DS 0008 00001¹. The original copy comes from Palembang, Sumatra, from the private collection of Masagus Aminuddin. According to a recent study by Alan Darmawan [Darmawan 2025], this manuscript once belonged to the royal family of Palembang Sultanate². Along with the Arabic text of the creed, it contains translation to Malay between the lines and two levels of commentaries, also in Malay, that constitute the manuscript’s complex and peculiar anatomy. Created at the dawn of the age of print, which is believed to have

¹ See <https://www.hmmcloud.org/dreamsea/detail.php?msid=1624> (accessed on 11.04.2024). I also wish to thank Dr. Oman Fathurahman and Muhammad Nida’ Fadlan for granting me access to a high-quality digital copy of the manuscript.

² The royal family of Palembang Sultanate (1675–1825) owned an extensive manuscript library which after the fall of the sultanate under the colonial powers was partly looted and partly passed down through generations of their descendants.

begin in the Islamic world around 1850 [Gelvin, Green 2013: 2], the copy represents Malay Islamic manuscript culture at the late stages of its development. Having persisted well into the 20th century, this culture engaged with a variety of paratextual elements, among them interlinear translation.

This case study attempts to reflect on the paratextual functions and nature of interlinear translations found in manuscripts from the Indonesian-Malay world. Paratexts have been described as “thresholds of interpretation” [Genette 1997b] and access [Paling 2002] which, in Indonesian contexts, not only frame the text but also “shape how people make sense of it, what they grow to anticipate and how they respond” [Ricci 2012: 196]. Translations, along with exegesis they often border on, appear to fit these definitions, as they do control the readers’ understanding of the text. Gérard Genette, whose synchronic study focused on the European print culture, does not list interlinear translation among different types of paratextual productions. However, it can beyond doubt be classified as such, being an auxiliary discourse dedicated to the service of something other than itself, i.e. the text [Genette 1997b: 12].

In the manuscript world, this auxiliary was manifested visually on the page: interlinear notes and marginal commentaries appear in smaller script and often sloppy handwriting, demonstrating their secondariness or subordination to the main text. The exemplar discussed in this essay is representative of this practice, as much as is it a graphic example of a range of paratexts occurring in Malay Islamic manuscripts. On the pages of DS 0008 00001, the hierarchical relationship between the text and paratexts corresponds to a similar one between the two languages — the sacred language of the scripture, Arabic, and the region’s language of Islam, Malay. In what follows, I address and question the power relations between the two bodies of text, i.e. the Arabic text and its Malay paratexts, and try to situate interlinear translation within Genette’s questionnaire for paratextual elements [Genette 1997b: 4–13] by means of defining its spatial, temporal, substantial, pragmatic, and functional features.

2. A “bearded” book and its paratexts

One of the terms used in the Indonesian-Malay world to describe manuscripts with interlinear layout is *kitab jenggotan* — *kitab* standing

for an Arabographic book and *jenggotan* for ‘beard’. In such “bearded books”, the Arabic *matn* (original text — a word for ‘text’ in Arabic which also has a meaning of ‘backbone’) is usually widely spaced, while translation is written in smaller *Jawi* or *pegon* scripts³ and arranged in inclined fragments under the line. Hanging hooked to the corresponding sections of the source, such translations resemble long beards of respectable Islamic scholars. Not all interlinear notes are translations, some are glosses in the Arabic language; some are placed above the source, some form parallel lines instead of diagonal fragments. However, the pattern described above appears to be more common in 19th-century manuscripts, and such a layout is employed in the Palembang manuscript of *Umm al-barāhīn* (see *Fig. 1*). Furthermore, the text of the creed in it is not just “bearded”, but rather “shagged”: surrounded by layers of translations and commentaries, the *matn* sinks in a body of paratexts that altogether surpass it in size.

The manuscript is virtually a material and visual manifestation of the long and fascinating afterlife of al-Sanūsī’s work in the Indonesian-Malay world. The *Mother of Arguments*, also known as “al-Sanūsī’s short catechism” (*al-‘Aqīdah al-sanūsiyyah al-ṣuġrā*) was written as part of the theologian’s educational project aimed at teaching the basics of Islamic faith to students on different levels [Olsen 2020: 106–110]. Over the centuries, the creed gained popularity and spread around the Islamic world, having become a basis for an extensive body of translations and commentaries. In the Indonesian-Malay region, where *Umm al-barāhīn* became the most popular work on Ash‘arite⁴ doctrine, a big cluster of “secondary” texts grew around it: commentaries, renderings, glosses, versifications, and even a whole new local genre of Islamic creed writing (see [Bruckmayr 2017]). The manuscript from Palembang brings together on its pages some of these texts: they follow, surround, and interline the text of the catechism, “fleshing out” the “skeleton” of the *matn* [Proudfoot 2002: 120].

³*Jawi* is a modified Arabic script used for writing in Malay, Acehnese, Minangkabau, and some other languages of Islamic Southeast Asia. *Pegon* is a similar Arabographic writing system used for Javanese, Sundanese, and Madurese.

⁴Ash‘arism is one of the major schools of Sunni theological thought that has become predominant in Indonesia.

Fig. 1. DS 0008 00001, f. 4r. DREAMSEA digital collection, used under Creative Commons CC BY-NC 4.0 License

Of the 152 pages of the manuscript, only some 48 (ff. 2v — 26r) are occupied by the original Arabic text of *Umm al-barāhīn*⁵. The creed is followed by a Malay commentary on it, which is twice as long as the source (ff. 27v — 73v). The commentary (*sharḥ*), or rather a rendering, is a well-known work in its own right: composed in 1756–57 by Muḥammad Zayn al-Faqīh Jalāluddīn al-Āshī, a scholar from Aceh, and known under the title *Bidāyat al-hidāyah*, this “Malay version” of *Umm al-barāhīn* has been being copied, published, and read independently of the original up to the present day. In the manuscript under discussion, this text can be seen as either a paratext or a separate text that is just placed next to another piece of writing, which often happens in handwritten codices. On the one hand, it is not impossible for a text to form a paratext of another; on the other, the relationship between *Umm al-barāhīn* and *Bidāyat al-hidāyah* can be rather described in terms of what Genette defines as metatextuality [Genette 1997a: 4]. In the scholar’s five-element system of transtextualities [Genette 1997a: 1–7; Macksey 1997: xviii–xix], paratextuality is only one of the types that, however, in some cases overlaps with others.

On the pages dedicated to *Umm al-barāhīn*, the main text still gives half of the space, if not more, to paratexts. Here two types of those come into play, sharing the page with the *matn*: translation between the lines and commentaries in the margins — both Malay texts written in a smaller Jawi script. The main Arabic text is written in bigger letters and occupies a central position on the page, its lines widely spaced and frame rulings creating capacious margins. Designed to accommodate notes and glosses, interlinear and marginal spaces not just invite paratexts but make them indispensable. At the same time, a hierarchy between the primary and the secondary, the authoritative and the exegetic, Arabic and Malay is still established through the main text’s bigger script and central position. Placing translation between the lines and commentaries in the margins seems to draw a distinction between the two types of paratext; however, in Indonesian-Malay Islamic manuscript cultures, the boundaries between “translation” and

⁵ The text of the catechism has been published and translated. See the Arabic text in: [Hāshiyah 2015: 14–22]; an English translation in: [Islamic Creeds 1994: 90–97]; and a summary in: [Wensinck 2008: 275–76].

“interpretation” are blurred, and the two often work towards the same goal, that is explanation. The twofold paratextual structure found in the manuscript, in this light, offers a solution to a debate between two types of translation: literal and interpretative [Pink 2020: 339].

Hanging in diagonal fragments between the lines, the interlinear translation is rather literal, word-for-word, almost every Arabic word or grammatical form finding their “equivalents” in Malay — which results in the somewhat artificial Malay language of the resulting text⁶. However, this very faithful translation still allows occasional explanatory digressions from the source, despite the presence of proper exegetical notes on the same page. This combination of literality and elucidations served the dual pedagogical function of interlinear translation, which was and still is used in Indonesia’s Islamic education to teach students both the Arabic language and the contents of authoritative texts (see [Iankovskaia 2023, 2024]). Al-Sanūsī’s “short” catechism was usually taught to beginners with a basic command of Arabic, therefore both word-by-word translation and explanatory remarks were employed to convey the meaning of the text. Literal as it is, the translation in the Palembang manuscript still reads coherently and independently of the Arabic text, forming a self-consistent narrative. Playing a paratextual role in this particular copy, it has a potential to break away from the text and start a life of its own — as it happened to some other translations of *Umm al-barāhīn* that were published and retranslated separately as “Malay versions” of the creed (see [Cabaton 1904; Che’ Razi Jusoh 2016]).

For an educational system where teaching Arabic as a foreign language had not taken shape as a separate discipline [Versteegh 2006: 4–5], the functions of interlinear translations cannot be discussed in detachment from those of commentaries, of which translation was an “extended arm” [Kooria 2022: 322]. Teaching texts, such as *Umm al-barāhīn*, were transmitted to new generations of Muslims in a similar way both in Arabic- and non-Arabic-speaking Islamic worlds: they were recited and explained (either in Arabic or a vernacular if needed) by the teacher in front of the students who tried to memorise the *matn* and scribbled translations or glosses in their

⁶ On the mechanicity of translations from Arabic and the Arabicised literary Malay language that resulted from it, see [Riddell 2002; Ronkel 1899].

copies⁷. A curriculum of such basic texts used for teaching Islamic sciences⁸ had formed in the Islamic world by the 16th century, commentaries having become a key medium of mastering these texts: “the teaching texts were encased in multiple layers of subsequent commentary, consisting of primary commentaries (*shurūḥ*, sing. *sharḥ*) written by either the *matn* author or, more commonly, later scholars; glosses (*ḥawāshī*, sing. *ḥāshiya*), usually but not always based on commentaries; and sometimes tertiary commentaries (*taqārīr*, sing. *taqrīr*), that is, commentaries on glosses on commentaries” [El Shamsy 2020: 32]. Such postclassical⁹ textual clusters found their material manifestations in multi-layered manuscripts that continued to be produced up to the 19th century and beyond.

In the Indonesian-Malay world, Islamic teaching texts are known as *kitab kuning* (‘yellow books’) — a category that al-Sanūsī’s *Umm al-barāhīn* belongs to. The basis of this body of texts is constituted by Arabic works dating back to between the 10th and 15th centuries, around which a range of later texts, in either Arabic or Malay, has been built [Bruinessen 1994: 121; 2012: 99]. These texts present themselves as something secondary: commentaries, summaries, renderings, or translations. In manuscripts, they appear as paratexts between the lines or in the margins; or as metatexts detached from the source. Demonstrating their subordination to the original, these texts reinforce and reproduce the religious and cultural authority of the classical works. But are they as auxiliary as they are trying to seem? Could it be that they overshadow the base text, tackling its message and reshaping it before handing off to the reader?

“The commentary, the stereotypical genre of postclassical scholarship, is characterized by a particular hierarchy of authority among its textual layers. On the one hand, a commentary attributes a privileged status to the work commented upon and presents itself primarily as serving and expounding the base text (...) But on the other hand, by superimposing itself textually on the base

⁷ For late 19th-century Sumatra, this practice has been described by Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje [Snouck Hurgronje 1906: 29–30].

⁸ Islamic sciences (‘*ulūm al-dīn*’) are a range of religious disciplines that include theology (*kalām* or *uṣūl al-dīn*), interpretation of the Quran (*tafsīr*), and law (*fiqh*).

⁹ The postclassical period in Islamic intellectual history (c. 1100–1900) is believed to have followed the so-called Islamic Golden Age.

text, the commentary effectively determines the latter's meaning; and in quantitative terms, the commentary overwhelms the base text, whose reproduction usually represents only a small fraction of the commentary work. As successive layers of commentary are added over the first layer, the actual words of the base text sometimes disappear entirely" [El Shamsy 2020: 39–40].

In the postclassical Islamic book culture, which has been criticised for its traditionalism and textual scholasticism, agglomerations of commentaries developed as means for maintaining the continuity between the present and the past, as well as that for ensuring the “correct” understanding of the authoritative texts. Texts did not speak directly to the readers, but were conveyed to them through a teacher or commentator, who supervised the readers' comprehension of the content in order to prevent unauthorised (mis)interpretation. Commentaries (and translations) acted not just as thresholds, but rather as filters that the meaning of a text was sifted through, or even firewalls limiting the readers' access to the primary source. For non-Arabic-speaking Muslims with their often very basic command of the source language, and especially for students at the beginner level who engaged with *Umm al-barāhīn*, this access was also naturally limited by the language barrier. The *matn* was frequently read aloud and memorised with little understanding, while understanding was facilitated through translations and explanations in the mother tongue.

In this light, the power relationship between a text and its interlinear translation appears more complex than a simple hierarchy. Written in the sacred language of the Quran, by a reputable Middle Eastern scholar, the text was cherished and held in higher esteem, but it was primarily the translation that was read — if by reading we mean understanding the meaning, not simply vocalising the text. Translation mediated the text to the readers, and this endowed it with certain power over the reception. In cases of literal translation, such as in the manuscript addressed in this essay, this power was limited and could be only exercised through word choices. However, in many manuscripts from the Indonesian-Malay world one can find interlinear translations that depart rather far from the source (see [Iankovskaia 2023, 2025]), interpreting the text in creative and sometimes odd ways¹⁰. “Although in interlinear translations the rules were more

¹⁰Anthony Johns [Johns 2009: 54–55] describes such translations as ‘open adaptations’ (*saduran terbuka*).

set and rigid and there was less room for imagination and flexibility than in other forms of translation and adaptation, the initial rigidity and consistency somewhat paradoxically then allowed for change which was also consistent and thus widespread, opening the door to much creativity and variation” [Ricci 2016: 79]. Allowing certain flexibility, these cross-lingual paratexts seem indeed to be thresholds of interpretation, which not only guard the door but also offer the readers a lens to see what is behind it.

3. What is between the lines?

In his comprehensive study of paratexts, Genette does not address interlinear translation — although it can occasionally be found in printed books. However, the scholar provides an outline for describing paratextual productions: “defining a paratextual element consists of determining its location (the question *where?*); the date of its appearance and, if need be, its disappearance (*when?*); its mode of existence, verbal or other (*how?*); the characteristics of its situation of communication — its sender and addressee (*from whom? to whom?*); and the functions that its message aims to fulfil (*to do what?*)” [Genette 1997b: 4]. Let us try to answer these questions for interlinear translation as practised in the Indonesian-Malay world in the 19th century, and for the one found in the Palembang manuscript of *Umm al-barāhīn* in particular.

For the location of interlinear translation, the answer is simple — it is always between the lines. What differs is its position with respect to the main text. In Arabographic manuscripts from the region, such translations usually appear below the line, but can also occur above¹¹. In most cases they are fragmented into units placed at an angle of up to 45° towards the corresponding parts of the original text. But sometimes these fragments are almost horizontal, up to forming parallel lines of translation alternating with the source (see, for example, the oldest known manuscript with interlinear translation in [al-Attas 1988: 99–148]). Not all interlinear translations are line-by-line, some are rather occasional glosses scattered around

¹¹ Hereafter such general observations are based on the author’s experience of browsing digital copies of manuscripts in online repositories such as the British Library Endangered Archives, Leiden University Libraries, DREAMSEA, Qalamos, etc.

the text. Also not all of them reach the end of a manuscript: it seems indeed more typical of them to end abruptly somewhere in the middle of the source text, or even after the first few pages. In the Palembang manuscript, this does not happen: the translation is provided for the whole text, in relatively neat handwriting, which apparently indicates that it was thoroughly copied from a written source rather than scribbled down by a sloppy hand during the class. Apart from this, the interlinear translation in the manuscript appears to represent a most typical layout of its kind.

The question *when?* is, quite the opposite, anything but simple. The only safe thing to say is that interlinear translation is composed after the source text, but when exactly is in most cases impossible to tell. The majority of manuscripts are undated, and even if a date is known or can be roughly guessed, it is not necessary the same for the main text and its translation. Some translations appear to be written by the same hand as the text, others not. But even in the first case, it is hardly possible to deduce whether the translation was copied immediately after the text, from the same earlier bilingual manuscript, or was added by the same scribe (possibly years) later, having been either copied from a different written source or written down from a teacher's dictation. Another remarkable feature of interlinear translation as practised in the Indonesian-Malay world is that, having once been composed, a translation did not freeze or disappear but continued being modified in the process of transmission, which combined both written and oral practices (see [Iankovskaia 2025]). For the same *matn*, there often exist many different versions of interlinear translation which might be related to each other to different extents.

After a paratext's temporal situation, Genette suggests discussing its mode of existence, or "substantial status", that can be verbal, iconic, material, or factual [Genette 1997b: 7]. Interlinear translation is clearly verbal, although on rare occasions it can interact with non-textual elements such as marks, frames, or coloured ink. In DS 0008 00001, however, none of these seem to be present in the interlinear space. At the same time, such elements are found in the other fields of the manuscript: frame rulings separate marginal glosses from the main text and from each other, while some words and phrases within both the *matn* and commentaries are written in red ink. A peculiar layout, in particular, is found in the beginning of the manuscript (ff. 1v — 2r): the main text represented by a single

*Basmala*¹² is written vertically and occupies only a narrow framed stripe in the middle of the page, while the rest of the space is, in fact, very wide margins dedicated to exegetic paratexts (see *Fig. 2*).

The next question is about the sender and the addressee of a paratextual element, i.e. its authors and audiences. The authors of interlinear translations, that is translators, are almost always not known, and this is also the case with the Palembang manuscript. However, both they and their audiences belonged to the Islamic educational milieu of the time. Texts were studied in Islamic schools¹³ and informal study circles, where students would bring their copies of the *matn* and scribble the teacher's interpretation between the lines. Roughly speaking, interlinear translations were addressed by a teacher to a student. But in practice, many actors were involved in shaping such a paratext. A teacher would not translate the text from the scratch, but rather used already existing notes by earlier scholars, slightly modifying the translation while dictating it to the class. The students, in their turn, could also corrupt it in the process of writing down, making an involuntary contribution. Furthermore, copies could be made by students from their peers' notes, and students' notes could be checked and corrected by the teacher. The "authorship" was thereby distributed between many teachers and students who participated in a chain of transmission. As for the audiences that interlinear translations aimed at, those were students at different levels of their studies: while line-by-line literal translation was helpful for beginners, isolated translations of difficult words or phrases could be a learning aid for those at more advanced levels.

The Palembang manuscript of *Umm al-barāhīn* represents the first case, the literal translation it contains corresponding to the text's pedagogical agenda. Originally composed for beginners, in the Indonesian-Malay world the creed was taught to beginners not only in studies of Islamic doctrine, but also to those in Arabic language. This brings us to the last question posed by Genette, that is to the functional aspect of a paratext, its message. Translation communicates both **information** and **interpretation**, the ratio between the two depending on its faithfulness to the source. Interlinear

¹² *Bismillāh al-raḥman al-raḥīm* ('In the name of God, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful'), the phrase commonly used as an opening line in Islamic manuscripts.

¹³ Known as *pesantren* in Java and *surau* or *dayah* in Sumatra.

دوقوت ارتوران لبسم الله ایزاهند و ذکر کار
مقام حقیقی دان کرد فوزه اولاد ان کتیا رضایی
دین کا عفت ناصحه

بیر و الله ایزه تمام دان ادوقوت شیخ محمد قنایه
نام ایزه ذات واجب الوجود شیخ بر صفت کمال
دان مهملو شیخ بر صفت کلور شیخ دان مستوی شیخ
دکتا کن صفت کمال ایزه یا شیخ سلسلی صفت شیخ
دکتا کن صفت کلور شیخ ایزه جلوه کلت الله ایزه
جوهر انجم انور عرضی

ادوقوت الرحیمی ایزه صفت فعل شیخ تربیت کن
در زندقه شیخ دان الرحیمی ایزه یا یکت دخی معنایه
از قیاس شیخ مالات دالم بوم دان دیاتسی بوم
سفره فرمان الله تعالی و ما عن درایت فی الارض
الاعلی الله تعالی و دان تعلقن ایزه بر تکت
کند شیخ حالین به الله سبحانه و تعالی جلوه در شیخ
اورش کیت او سببین در دهو لکن لفظ الرحمن
اتسی الرحیم که بعد ادوقوت الرحیمی ایزه معنایه
رزق دان و وضع دالم دنیا و ایزه دنیا ایت
تردهو کند اخرخ

ادوقوت الرحیم ساد صفت افعل الله سبحانه و تعالی
کندر کله جهات شیخ عن دالم اخر شیخ یا یکت واجب
دخی معنی تفصل الله تعالی ممدی رحمة اتسی
سکله بیان شیخ عن دالم اخر شیخ سفره فرمان
الله تعالی

30

الله

الله

الله

Fig. 2. DS 0008 00001, f. 1v. DREAMSEA digital collection, used under Creative Commons CC BY-NC 4.0 License

translation of a teaching text aims at mediating this text to the readers, but the ultimate goal is pedagogical, i.e. teaching both Arabic and Islam. The word-for-word translation found in the Palembang manuscript accomplishes this double mission by communicating the meanings of words and structure of Arabic sentence on the one hand, and the message of the text, in its authorised interpretation, on the other.

4. Conclusion

In this brief essay, I have attempted to explore the paratextual features of interlinear translation as practised in the Indonesian-Malay world by the 19th century. The observations made are still very preliminary and require further development. Building on Genette's questionnaire, I have tried to describe interlinear translation as a regionally specific type of paratext. Just like the scholar's work, this small study is rather synchronic than diachronic, as it looks into the paratextual practice under discussion at a certain stage of its historical development. Focusing on a manuscript representative of the tradition, it zooms into the history of a paratextual element capturing the shapes it took and practices that surrounded it during a particular period. Mediating the main text to the reader, interlinear translation proves to be one of the many types of paratext, with its own history and specific features.

“Some of these [paratextual] elements are as old as literature; others came into being — or acquired their official status, after centuries of ‘secret life’ that constitute their prehistory — with the invention of the book; others, with the birth of journalism and the modern media. Others disappeared in the meantime; and quite often some replace others so as to perform, for better or worse, an analogous role. Finally, some seem to have undergone, and to be undergoing still, a more rapid or more significant evolution than others ⟨...⟩ The general history of the paratext, punctuated by the stages of a technological evolution that supplies it with means and opportunities, would no doubt be the history of those ceaseless phenomena of sliding, substitution, compensation, and innovation which ensure, with the passing centuries, the continuation and to some extent the development of the paratext's efficacy” [Genette 1997b: 14]. Part of this history appears to be that of interlinear translation.

A history of interlinear translation, both in the Indonesian-Malay region and beyond, is yet to be written. It would be closely intertwined with histories of notes and commentaries, religion and language teaching, translation and multilingualism. In the Indonesian-Malay world, this textual practice, albeit in a different form, is likely to have existed before the advance of Islam; and it did not disappear with the arrival of print and beginning of the digital age, having shifted from manuscripts to printed *kitab kuning* and their digital copies, as well as to students' notebooks and whiteboards in classrooms. A history of interlinear translation would be indeed that of evolution and reinvention, and the material and visual manifestations it found in Malay Islamic manuscript culture would mark in it an essential stage.

References

- al-Attas 1988 — Syed Muhammad Naquib al-Attas. *The Oldest Known Malay Manuscript: A 16th Century Malay Translation of the 'Aqā'id of al-Nasafi*. Kuala Lumpur: University of Malaya, 1988.
- Bruckmayr 2017 — P. Bruckmayr. The *šarḥ* / *ḥāšīya* Phenomenon in Southeast Asia. From al-Sanūsī's *Umm al-Barāhīn* to Malay *Sifat Dua Puluh* Literature. *MIDĒO*. 2017. Vol. 32. P. 27–52.
- Bruinessen 1994 — M. van Bruinessen. Pesantren and Kitab Kuning: Continuity and Change in a Tradition of Religious Learning. W. Marschall (ed.). *Texts from the Islands: Oral and Written Traditions of Indonesia and the Malay World*. Berne: University of Berne Institute of Ethnology, 1994. P. 121–146.
- Bruinessen 2012 — M. van Bruinessen. *Kitab Kuning, Pesantren dan Tarekat*. Yogyakarta: Gading Publishing, 2012.
- Cabaton 1904 — A. Cabaton. Une traduction interlinéaire malaise de la 'Aqīda d'al-Senūsī. *Journal Asiatique*. 1904. Vol. 10. P. 115–145.
- Che' Razi Jusoh 2016 — Che' Razi Jusoh. *The Malay Exposition of al-Sanūsī's Umm al-Barāhīn*. Selangor: Islamic and Strategic Studies Institute, 2016.
- Darmawan 2025 — A. Darmawan. Where are the Palembang Kraton Manuscripts? Trajectories of a Royal Library. *Archipel*. 2025. Vol. 110 (forthcoming).
- El Shamsy 2020 — A. El Shamsy. *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics: How Editors and Print Culture Transformed an Intellectual Tradition*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2020.
- Gelvin, Green 2013 — J. L. Gelvin, N. Green. Introduction. Global Muslims in the Age of Steam and Print. J. L. Gelvin, N. Green (eds.). *Global Muslims in the Age of Steam and Print*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2013. P. 1–22.

- Genette 1997a — G. Genette. *Palimpsests. Literature in the Second Degree*. Lincoln: London: University of Nebraska Press, 1997.
- Genette 1997b — G. Genette. *Paratexts: Thresholds of Interpretation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997.
- Hāshiyah 2015 — *Hāshiyah al-'allāmah al-shaikh Ibrāhīm al-Bayjūrī 'alā Umm al-barāhīn*. Istanbul: Hāšimī, 2015.
- Iankovskaia 2023 — A. Iankovskaia. Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje. *Archipel*. 2023. Vol. 106. P. 89–124.
- Iankovskaia 2024 — A. Iankovskaia. Reading Arabic in Sumatra. Interlinear Translation in Didactic Contexts. *Indonesia and the Malay World*. 2024. Vol. 52 (153). P. 221–242.
- Iankovskaia 2025 — A. Iankovskaia. On ‘Hanging Meaning’ and Its Transmission. Tracing a Didactic Poem from Aceh. *Archipel*. 2025. Vol. 107. P. 119–138.
- Islamic Creeds 1994 — W. Montgomery Watt (transl., comp.). *Islamic Creeds. A Selection*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 1994.
- Johns 2009 — A. H. Johns. “Penerjemahan” bahasa Arab ke dalam bahasa Melayu: sebuah renungan. H. Chamber-Loir (ed.). *Sadur: sejarah terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*. Jakarta: Gramedia, 2009. P. 49–58.
- Kooria 2022 — M. Kooria. Islamic Law in Circulation: Shāfi‘ī Texts across the Indian Ocean and the Mediterranean. Cambridge; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2022.
- Macksey 1997 — R. Macksey. Foreword. G. Genette. *Paratexts: Thresholds of Interpretation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997. P. xi–xxiii.
- Olson 2020 — C. Olson. Beyond the Avicennian Turn: The Creeds of Muḥammad b. Yūsuf al-Sanūsī (d. 895/1490). *Studia Islamica*. 2020. Vol. 115 (1). P. 101–140.
- Paling 2002 — S. Paling. Thresholds of Access: Paratextuality and Classification. *Journal of Education for Library and Information Science*. 2002. Vol. 43. No. 2. P. 134–143.
- Pink 2020 — J. Pink. The *Kyai*’s Voice and the Arabic Qur’an; Translation, Orality, and Print in Modern Java. *Wacana, Journal of the Humanities of Indonesia*. 2020. Vol. 21. No. 3. P. 329–359.
- Ricci 2012 — R. Ricci. Thresholds of Interpretation on the Threshold of Change: Paratexts in Late 19th-century Javanese Manuscripts. *Journal of Islamic Manuscripts*. 2012. Vol. 3. P. 185–210.
- Ricci 2016 — R. Ricci. Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation. *Journal of World Literature*. 2016. Vol. 1 (1). P. 68–80.
- Riddell 2002 — P. G. Riddell. Literal Translation, Sacred Scripture and Kitab Malay. *Studia Islamica*. 2002. Vol. 9 (1). P. 1–26.
- Ronkel 1899 — P. S. van Ronkel. Over de invloed der Arabische syntaxis op de Maleische. *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*. 1899. Vol. 41. P. 498–528.

- Snouck Hurgronje 1906 — C. Snouck Hurgronje. *The Acehnese*. Vol. 2. Leiden: Brill, 1906.
- Versteegh 2006 — K. Versteegh. History of Arabic Language Teaching. K. M. Wahba, Z. A. Taha, L. England (eds.). *Handbook for Arabic Language Teaching Professionals in the 21st Century*. Mahwah; London: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 2006. P. 3–12.
- Wensinck 2008 — A. J. Wensinck. *The Muslim Creed. Its Genesis and Historical Development*. Oxford: Routledge, 2008.

Sources

DS 0008 00001, DREAMSEA Repository. Available at: <https://www.hmmlcloud.org/dreamsea/detail.php?msid=1624> (accessed on 11.04.2024).

Получено/received 16.01.2025

Принято/accepted 3.02.2025